

5. W. VANDER VEER and F. JELLINEK, *Rec. Trav. Chim. Pays Bas*, 1966, **85**, 842.
6. M. G. KING and G. P. MCQUILLAN, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1967, 898.
7. P. NICPON and D. W. MEREK, *Chem. Commun.*, 1966, 398.
8. M. NEGOU and P. SPACU, *An. Univ. Bucuresti Chim.*, 1970, **19**, 93.
9. L. MALATESTA, *Gass. Chim. ital.*, 1947, **77**, 509.
10. L. S. D. GLASSER, L. INGRAM, M. G. KING and G. P. MCQUILLAN, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1969, 2501.
11. E. W. AINSCOUGH, H. A. BERGEN and A. M. BRODIR, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.*, 1976, **17**, 1649.
12. D. A. WHEATLAND, R. W. WALDRON and C. H. CLAPP, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 2340.
13. S. S. SANDHU and T. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**, 829.
14. S. S. SANDHU and T. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1086.
15. T. S. LOBANA and S. S. SANDHU, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **4**, 37; *Chem. Abs.*, 1979, **91**, 67636j.

Complexes of Neodymium(III) with Glycine, Iminodiacetic Acid and Nitrilotriacetic Acid : A Polarographic Study

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AMINO acids have been extensively used for the complex formation with various metals¹⁻⁵. Among the amino acids the chelating ability of the derivatives of acetic acid is particularly noteworthy. In recent years, rare earth complexes with various complexing agents have been studied employing pH titration, potentiometric and spectrophotometric techniques etc⁶⁻⁹. However, little attention has been given on the polarographic study of the rare earth complexes. In the present communication the authors have reported the polarographic study of Nd(III) complexes with glycine, iminodiacetic acid and nitrilotriacetic acids.

Experimental

Stock solutions of 0.01 M glycine (E. merck, Germany), iminodiacetic acid (BDH) and nitrilotriacetic acid (Reanel, Hungary) were prepared in carbon dioxide free double distilled water. The Nd(III) solution was prepared by dissolving a calculated quantity of the metal oxide in minimum amount of dil. hydrochloric acid (AnalaR). The metal solution was standardised by EDTA method¹⁰.

Potassium chloride 2.0 M and gelatin (AnalaR), solution were prepared in double distilled water.

A preliminary experimental set was prepared by keeping overall concentration of potassium chloride, gelatin and Nd(III) fixed at 1.0 M, 0.01% and 2 m M respectively. In the other sets, in addition to the above metal ion, supporting electrolyte and gelatin concentrations, the ligand concentration was varied from 0.25 m M to 3.0 m M. The ionic strength was fixed at 1.0 by adjusting with potassium chloride. Hydrochloric acid was used to fix the pH value of the solution at 2.75 ± 0.02.

Current-Voltage curves were obtained by using a C.I.C (Baroda, India) polarograph, the capillary used had m value of 2.15 mg/sec, and drop time of 3.1 sec/drop at -1.765 V vs SCE, when measured in an air free 1.0 M KCl solution at 45 cm of effective height of mercury ($m^{2/3}t^{1/3} = 2.15 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/3}$). Dissolved oxygen was removed by passing purified nitrogen gas through the solutions and the polarograms were recorded. For adjusting pH at 2.75 ± 0.02 an Elico digital pH meter was used. All the measurements were carried out at room temperature 32 ± 0.1°.

Results and Discussion

Nd(III) gives a well defined reversible reduction wave in 1.0 M potassium chloride plus 0.01% gelatin at pH 2.75¹¹⁻¹². The reduction of Nd(III) and Nd(III)-complexes with all the three ligands were found to be of diffusion controlled nature as the plots of i vs $\sqrt{h}$ ($\sqrt{\text{effective height of mercury column}}$) yielded straight lines passing through the origin. An analysis of the plots of E_{dme} vs $\log I/1d-I$ and $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ values for the simple Nd(III) and for its complexes with all the three ligands i.e., (substituted amino gr. derivatives of acetic acid) revealed a reversible nature of the reduction waves.

Effect of Ligand Concentration :

At pH 2.75 the half wave potential of Nd(III) shifted to more negative values on increasing the concentration of ligands.

A Lingane¹³ treatment of the data revealed 1 : 1 complexes of Nd(III) with all the three ligands e.g., glycine, iminodiacetic acid and nitrilotriacetic acid. The metal ligand ratio and the values of the stability constants have been tabulated below.

TABLE

Stability Constants of Nd(III) Complexes

1. Nd(III)-Glycine	$\log \beta$	4.00
2. Nd(III)-Iminodiacetic acid	$\log \beta$	4.36
3. Nd(III)-Nitrilotriacetic acid	$\log \beta$	4.78

It is clear from the data that the metal ligand stability constants for the three amino acids under examination follow the order of glycine < iminodiacetic acid and < nitrilotriacetic acid, which is in excellent agreement with the results reported by Schwarzenbach and Biedermann². The increased values of the metal ligand stability constants in the said order may be explained on the basis of the presence of 2 acetic acid groups in IDA and 3 acetic acid groups in NTA, which render these ligands a good deal more reactive towards the generality of the cations, than glycine, as a result of which increased liganding ability is observed from glycine to NTA.

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References

1. FLOOD and LORCES, *Tids, Kjems, Bergsvsen Met.*, 1945, **6**, 83.
2. SCHWARZENBACH and BIEDERMANN, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1948, **31**, 338.
3. KUEBLER and BAILAR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 3535.
4. A. H. NAKAHARA, YAMATA and H. MATSUMATA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1964, **37**, 1137.
5. M. KISHITA, A. NOKHARA and M. KURO, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1964, **17**, 810.
6. R. C. AGRAWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 984.
7. S. D. MAKHIJANI and SANGAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 670.
8. V. D. DESHPANDE and S. S. DARA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 837.
9. P. V. TAKALKAR and V. RAMCHANDRA RAO, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 2103.
10. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical uses of ethylene diamine tetraacetic acid", (D. Van Nostrand Company Inc.) p. 1957, 174, 181.
11. ESTERL and G. GLOCKLER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1844.
12. K. S. PITRE and V. K. CHITALE, *Convention of Chem.*, 1979, Anal, 5.
13. J. J. LINGAN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, **21**, 1.

Micro Determination of Some Azo Dyes with N-bromosaccharin

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AZO compounds constitute an important group of colouring matters known as azo dyes, most of which are used as indicators or in dyeing fibres. There are various methods of analysis of azo compounds¹⁻³, the most recent one⁴ involving bromination with N-bromosuccinimide.

Yet another quick and convenient method has been developed by the present authors for the micro determination of azo dyes using N-bromosaccharin which is a stable and faster brominating and oxidising agent⁵. The sample was allowed to react with excess of N-bromosaccharin in presence of acetic acid for 5-10 minutes at room temperature (25°). After the reaction was over the unconsumed reagent was determined iodometrically. The present method gives highly accurate and reproducible results within an error of 0.5% in most of the cases.

Experimental

A stock solution of each sample was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount of the sample in distilled water or in 10% acetic acid in a 100 ml volumetric flask. All the samples were purified by recrystallisation and their purity was checked by a constant melting point.

An aliquot containing 1-3 mg of the sample was taken in a 100 ml iodine flask. 10 ml 0.02 M solution of N-bromosaccharin (prepared by dissolving 1.3116 g N-bromosaccharin in glacial acetic acid and made upto 250 ml) was added to it. The flask was stoppered and allowed to stand for 5-10 minutes at room temperature (25°) with occasional shaking. After the reaction was over the stopper was washed with 5.0 ml distilled water and then 5.0 ml aqueous potassium iodide solution (10%) was added to it. The contents were shaken thoroughly and kept for a minute. The liberated iodine was titrated with standardised 0.01 M sodium thiosulphate solution using starch (1% aqueous solution) as indicator. A blank experiment was also run under identical conditions using all the reagents except the sample.

Calculation :

$$\text{mg of sample} = \frac{(B - A) \times M \times N}{n \times 2}$$

where, A = ml of sodium thiosulphate solution for sample ; B = ml of sodium thiosulphate solution for